

**IMPEDANCE RESPONSE FOR DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF
*Escherichia coli***

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ABSTRACT

Water is one of the absolute necessity for living things. However, based on the World Health Organization (WHO), drinking water contaminated by microorganisms, especially *Escherichia coli* (e-coli) became one of the causes of death in adults and infants. *Escherichia coli* is a bacterial indicator of the quality of drinking water in which *Escherichia coli* in water indicates that the water contaminated by feces. In recent years, immunosensors has attracted a lot of interest of researchers in various research because immunosensor has the potential to achieve fast results, inexpensive, and portable in a diagnosis. Using of Electrical Impedance Spectrometry (EIS) as a method of measuring immunosensor have been carried out in recent years to detect microorganisms in a material examination. The research was describe the impedance in a solution contain the bacteria e-coli in various concentrations administrated range of frequency. The sensor used gold-plated electrode and impedance converter is AD5933EBZ-Eval. The research was done at Departement of Medical Laboratory Technology STIKES Jend. A. Yani from April 15th until Mei 16th 2015. The results showed three characteristic impedance value from the solution administrated range of frequencies. The characteristic impedance are inductance (I), capacitive (C) and resistive (R). Impedance value increased proportional to the increase in the concentration of e-coli. The minimum concentration e-coli is 1/8 MF that can distinguish. The results indicate that the EIS method can be used as a sensor in the detection of e-coli in the solution.

Key words : bacterial indicator; immunosensors; Electrical Impedance Spectrometry; range of frequency; AD5933-Eval

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately a third of the world's population suffer from various diseases that are transmitted through drinking water contaminated by microorganisms. Every year about 13 million people died as a result of infection from drinking water, 2 million of whom are infants and children. Consuming water contaminated by pathogenic microorganisms, either water or water that is added to food, can cause a variety of gastrointestinal diseases [1]. One of microorganisms could contaminate drinking water is *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*).

Escherichia coli is a bacterium part of the normal microflora in the digestive tract of humans and warm-blooded animals [2]. *E. coli* bacteria is also an indicator of water

quality due to the presence in water indicates that the water is contaminated by faeces, which may also contain other pathogenic enteric microorganisms. *E. coli* becomes pathogenic if the number of bacteria in the digestive tract increases or outside the intestine. *E. coli* produces an enterotoxin that causes some cases of diarrhea [3]. Diarrhea still a major health problem among children, particularly in developing countries such as Indonesia [4]. The incidence of diarrhea more than a billion each year worldwide, 25-35 million of which occurred in Indonesia. Every child under five years old have two until eight times diarrhea per year with an average of 3.3 times [5]. Diarrhea is one of the main causes of high child mortality in the world. WHO reported that the leading causes of death among children under five years old is diarrhea (post neonatal) 14%, 8% malaria, injury 3%, 2% of HIV-AIDS. In Indonesia, diarrhea is still one of the major public health problem. there are 112,000 cases every year in Indonesia's population of diarrhea were experienced death in all age groups, in infants occurred 55,000 deaths [6].

The laws of the Republic of Indonesia No. 7 1996, wrote that the food is anything that comes from biological sources and water, whether treated or untreated, which is applied as a food or beverage for human consumption, including food additives, food raw materials, and other materials used in the preparation, processing, and or manufacture of food or drink. Given the definition of food have a broad scope, efforts to prevent contaminated food from a good possibility of biological, chemical, and other objects that can disrupt, harm and endanger human health. [7].

Microbiological test commonly performed to detect *Escherichia coli* in water is conventionally, that is the way the culture and test biochemical properties [8-10]. However, this conventional method generally takes 5-7 days to get a result. Deaths caused by this infectious, which one of them is diarrhea can be caused by several factors such as delays in detection and diagnosis, drug side effects and so on [11]. A long time relatively in the detection of microorganisms has prompted scientists to create tools to detect microorganisms quickly [12-14]. Some attempts to detect of pathogenic microorganisms have been carried out for the purpose of inspection speed, easy to use, accurate in examination and portable where such development can be useful for epidemic control in the management of treatment or diagnosis [15].

In the last years, multidisciplinary science was warm performed. One multidisciplinary science that developed is a biosensor. Biosensor is a combination of various tools that can analyze semiquantitatively or quantitatively from biological element

used as the target. Focus of the biosensor target is an enzyme [16], antibody [17], nucleic acid [18] and other. Biosensor consists of two major components, namely bioreceptor and transducer. Bioreceptor a biological component that is used as the target of a measure while the transducer is the component that reads the target obtained from bioreceptor into a measurable signal in the display [15]. One of the biosensor which is currently being developed is impedance biosensor. Impedance biosensors for detection of bacteria based on measuring changes in electrical properties of bacterial cells when they are attached to or associated with the electrode [12, 19]. Analysis the properties of materials obtained by applying electrical signals of different frequencies and measuring the corresponding electrical output signal [20].

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Preparation of microelectrode and Impedance Analyzer

Microelectrode used are gold-plated that consists 2 pieces of electrodes with a size of 1 mm thick. The distance between the electrode is 1 mm. Both ends of the electrodes are connected with impedance analyzer AD5933 EBZ-Eval connected to the computer device [Fig 1].

Fig 1. (a) sensor gold electrode layers; (b) Impedance Analyzer AD5933 EBZ-Eval

2.2 Microbiological Sample Preparation

Samples taken from a pure culture of *e-coli*. *Escherichia coli* culture diluted with binary rule of 1 McFarland (MF) to reach 1/32 McFarland (MF). *Escherichia coli* dilute by physiological saline solution (0.85% NaCl). Each tube dilution taken as much as 5 μ l then dropped into the electrode

3. Result and Discussion

Impedance value of the concentration of *e-coli* in the solution is calculated as a function of frequency. Results of impedance measurements of various concentrations of *e-coli* can be seen in Figure 2.

Fig 2. Impedance Characteristic of *E.coli* for Different Concentration.

Figure 2 shows the impedance characteristic of the measurement of the frequency function. The figure showed characteristics of *E.coli* in the dilution with different concentration in a solution varies depending on a given frequency. characteristics of e-coli is inductance at low frequency, capacitive in middle frequencies and resistive medium at high frequencies. NaCl solution without e-coli bacteria retains the impedance values, it shows the increasing frequency given on NaCl solution is not inhibited by the compound [16]. From that results the concentration of e-coli in the solution is still difficult to distinguish, so look for a particular frequency that can distinguish the impedance values against the concentration of E.coli. Frequency that allows to measure the concentration of E.coli in the solution at 450 Hz that is calculated by manually. The results shown in Figure 4.

Fig 3. Impedance value of *E.coli* for different concentration induced frequency at 450 Hz

Figure 3 above showed the impedance value in a solution with the highest concentration of e-coli has the highest impedance value anyway. Reduction of impedance showed from concentration of 1 MF to 1/8 MF. While the MF 1/8 to 1/32 does not look significant difference. Concentration 1/8 to 1/32 MF MF has an impedance value that is not much different from the diluting solution (physiological saline).

Impedance measurements using impedance analyzer AD5933EBZ-Eval can be used to detect *E. coli* in physiological saline solution, although concentration must more than 1/4 MF. Impedance value increased relative in proportion to the amount of e-coli in solution, where it exposure to a frequency of 450 Hz. Increased of impedance values indicate that *e-coli* bacteria were able to inhibit the flow of electricity [17-20], but it applies to a concentration of at least 1/4 MF of *e-coli*. Impedance value at concentration less than 1/4 MF of *e-coli* has a value that not vary much with the solution without *e-coli* that indicates the number of such bacteria are not able to inhibit a given frequency at 450 Hz [19, 21]. Measurement is still not possible to concentrations below 1/8 MF allows to be done in the development of instrumentation design.

4. Conclusion

The results showed impedance technique was able to detect *e-coli* in physiological NaCl solution. The minimum concentration that can detect the presence of *e-coli* using the AD5933EBZ-Eval EBZ is 1/8 MF. Increasing concentrations ranging from 1/8 MF to 1 MF given increasing in impedance value, so that it can be said impedance value is proportional to the concentration of *e-coli* in physiological NaCl solution. This study shows that the method of impedance can detect the existence of a material in a solution, which in this study material is Echerichia coli. Disadvantages of Impedance Analyzer AD5933EBZ-Eval provide opportunities for further development.

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6. References

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